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**Calculation of spin-wave eigenmodes in
confined nanostructures using a dynamic
matrix approach**

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TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DRESDEN

Abstract

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by Gwendolyn Quasebarth

Numerical micromagnetic simulations have been proven to be a powerful tool to obtain the spatial mode profiles and frequencies of spin waves, the elementary excitations of magnetic systems. To simulate these spin waves in arbitrary confined geometries, usually a dynamic simulation approach is implemented using a time integration of the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert (LLG) equation, followed by a Fourier transform to obtain mode profiles and frequencies. Although this method is very versatile, it cannot resolve degenerate modes and requires a-priori knowledge of the mode profiles. An alternative method is the dynamic matrix approach, which consists of a diagonalization of the linearized LLG equation and directly yields mode profiles and frequencies. In this thesis, such an approach is implemented in a program called TetraEigen, which builds upon TetraMag, an already existing micromagnetic code for finite element dynamical simulations. The implementation of the exchange and dipolar interactions, as well as magnetic anisotropy and external field is carried out and verified. Then, TetraEigen is applied to calculate the spin-wave modes in a disk with a displaced vortex and a vortex-state hemisphere. The results are compared to a flat vortex-state disk.

Kurzfassung in deutscher Sprache

Numerische mikromagnetische Simulationen haben sich als ein leistungsfähiges Werkzeug erwiesen, um die räumlichen Modenprofile und Frequenzen von Spinwellen, den elementaren Anregungen magnetischer Systeme, zu erhalten. Zur Simulation dieser Spinwellen in willkürlichen, begrenzten Geometrien wird in der Regel ein dynamischer Simulationsansatz unter Verwendung einer Zeitintegration der Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert-Gleichung (LLG) implementiert, gefolgt von einer Fourier-Transformation, um Modenprofile und Frequenzen zu erhalten. Obwohl diese Methode sehr vielseitig ist, kann sie degenerierte Moden nicht auflösen und erfordert a priori Kenntnisse der Modenprofile. Eine alternative Methode ist der dynamic matrix Ansatz, der aus einer Diagonalisierung der linearisierten LLG-Gleichung besteht und direkt Modenprofile und Frequenzen liefert. In dieser Arbeit wird ein solcher Ansatz in einem Programm namens TetraEigen implementiert, das auf TetraMag, einem bereits existierenden mikromagnetischen Code für dynamische Finite-Elemente-Simulationen, aufbaut. Die Implementierung der Austausch- und dipolaren Wechselwirkungen, sowie der magnetischen Anisotropie und des externen Feldes wird durchgeführt und verifiziert. Anschließend wird TetraEigen angewendet, um die Spinwellenmoden in einer Scheibe mit einem verschobenen Vortex und einer Halbkugel im Vortex-Zustand zu berechnen. Die Ergebnisse werden mit einer flachen Scheibe im Vortex-Zustand verglichen.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

In the study of spin waves (the elementary excitations of spin systems) in ferromagnetic materials, numerically obtaining frequencies and spatial profiles of the spin-wave modes in complex systems has often been a computationally expensive endeavour. While micromagnetic simulations implementing a dynamic simulation approach like Mumax³ [1] can simulate spin dynamics in simple systems using the Finite Differences Method relatively quickly, and the program TetraMag [2] is able to resolve curved systems with the more general Finite Element Method, they come at the risk of not finding all possible modes [3, 4].

The dynamic matrix approach expresses the linearized Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation of motion as an eigenvalue problem and solves it numerically. This allows for a quick calculation of oscillation modes in arbitrary geometries. There exist implementations of the dynamic matrix approach [3–6], but they are either limited to a specific problem or closed-source.

In this thesis, an implementation of the dynamic matrix approach is presented, which solves the lossless Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation of motion in confined geometries. This approach is implemented by the author in a program called TetraEigen. This implementation significantly simplifies the study of oscillation modes in confined (particularly curvilinear) systems, as it makes it possible to scan larger parameter spaces for spin-wave frequencies. It builds upon A. Kákay’s work with TetraMag [2], so it can be accelerated with GPUs. It will also be the first *open* implementation of an oscillation mode finder using an eigensolver. Although it can not describe the damping behavior of spin waves, spin-wave damping rates can be calculated after having found their profiles and frequencies using the method shown in [7].

1.2 Magnetic interactions

The dynamics of spins is governed by magnetic interactions. Each interaction can be described by assigning a magnetic field to it, which is derived from the corresponding energy functional. Here, we focus on the magnetic fields caused by the interactions, because they allow for a more direct description spin dynamics. Only affine interactions are considered, so for each interaction, we can define an operator $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_i$, such that the magnetic field \mathbf{H}_i is equal to $\mathbf{H}_{0,i} - \hat{\mathbf{N}}_i \mathbf{M}$, where \mathbf{M} is the magnetization and $\mathbf{H}_{0,i}$ does not depend on the (dynamic) magnetization or time. This representation will be useful in later sections.

1.2.1 Static external magnetic field (Zeemann interaction)

Static external fields do not depend on the magnetization of the considered ferromagnetic object. But they do affect the equilibrium configuration of the magnetization, which in turn influences the resulting oscillation modes.

1.2.2 Exchange interaction

The exchange interaction is a short-ranged interaction which favors parallel alignment of neighboring electron spins. As described in [8, p. 91], [9, sec. 4.2.7] and [4, p. 4], the exchange field can be written as

$$\mathbf{H}_{ex} = \Lambda_{ex}^2 \nabla^2 \mathbf{M} \quad (1.1)$$

in the continuum approximation, where Λ_{ex} is the exchange length. The exchange operator $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ex}$ is equal to

$$\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ex} = -\Lambda_{ex}^2 \nabla^2 \quad (1.2)$$

1.2.3 Magnetocrystalline anisotropy

Due to spin-orbit coupling, the energy of an electron depends on the orientation of its spin with respect to its orbital. The shape of the orbital in turn depends on the structure of the crystal lattice. If the interaction between the electron orbital and the crystal lattice is strong enough, this may lead to magnetocrystalline anisotropies which favor one or more axes of orientation of the magnetization. For a uniaxial anisotropy, which occurs for example in hexagonal crystals, this effect can be described by the anisotropy field [8, p. 85],

$$\mathbf{H}_{an} = \frac{2K_{u1}}{\mu_0 M_s^2} (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{u} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\implies \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{an} = -\frac{2K_{u1}}{\mu_0 M_s^2} \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u} \quad (1.4)$$

where \mathbf{u} is a normed vector pointing in the direction of the anisotropy axis, K_{u1} is the first-order uniaxial anisotropy constant, M_s is the saturation magnetization, and μ_0 is the vacuum permeability.

1.2.4 Interfacial Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya interaction (IDMI)

The interfacial Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction (IDMI) [10, 11] is a comparatively weak magnetic interaction which is important to explain magnetic skyrmions. It favors a continuous canting of spins. Its effective magnetic field can be described as [12]

$$\mathbf{H}_{dmi} = -\frac{2D}{\mu_0 M_s^2} (\mathbf{n}(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{M}) - \nabla(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})) \quad (1.5)$$

$$\implies \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{dmi} \mathbf{M} = \frac{2D}{\mu_0 M_s^2} ((\mathbf{n} \otimes \nabla) \mathbf{M} - \nabla(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})) \quad (1.6)$$

where D is the DMI constant, and \mathbf{n} is the surface normal vector.

1.2.5 Dipolar interaction

The magnetic dipolar (also called magnetostatic, demagnetizing) interaction is the classically known interaction between magnetic dipoles [9, p. 74]. Compared to the exchange interaction, it is a long-range interaction which leads to the formation of e.g. domain walls and magnetic vortex structures. The demagnetizing field \mathbf{H}_d can be expressed as [13, eq. 2]

$$\mathbf{H}_d = \int \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}') \left[\frac{3(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') \cdot (\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^5} - \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^3} \right] dV' \quad (1.7)$$

although it is computed numerically using the Fredkin-Koehler method [14], which represents the demagnetizing field as the gradient of the magnetostatic scalar potential U_d :

$$\mathbf{H}_d = -\nabla U_d \quad (1.8)$$

In some cases, for example in thin films, the dipolar interaction can be described as a shape anisotropy [9, sec. 6.7.2]. If describing the dipolar interaction via a shape anisotropy is possible for a given object, then the anisotropy calculation is a preferred representation, as it can be calculated (numerically) much faster.

1.3 Linearized Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation and spin waves

Magnetization dynamics are usually described using the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation [15, p. 33][16, § 69][17]. For numerical calculations, it is useful to write it using dimensionless quantities:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}}{\partial t} = - \left(\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{h} - \frac{\alpha}{1 + \alpha^2} \mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{h} \right) \quad (1.9)$$

where

- the dimensionless time t is measured in $(\gamma\mu_0 M_s)^{-1}$ (absolute value of gyromagnetic ratio times magnetic constant times saturation magnetization)
- the dimensionless magnetization \mathbf{m} and magnetic field \mathbf{h} are normalized by the saturation magnetization M_s
- α is the dimensionless Gilbert damping parameter [17]
- the dimensionless magnetic field \mathbf{h} is dependent on the magnetization \mathbf{m} , the exact dependence is described by different micromagnetic interactions.

The second term in the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation describes damping, which is useful to compute the equilibrium magnetization and to get information about the decay process of oscillation modes.

The elementary excitations of spin systems are called spin waves (or oscillation modes) [8, ch. 2]. This paper focuses on finding spin waves in arbitrary (especially curvilinear) systems, and a damping constant of $\alpha = 0$ is assumed, which significantly simplifies the search for spin waves. The decay of spin waves can be investigated after having found the fundamental oscillation modes [7].

We are now going to linearize the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation to find these elementary excitations of the equilibrium magnetization.

Because the magnetization and the field will be parallel in the equilibrium case and the magnitude of the equilibrium magnetization \mathbf{m}_0 will always equal one, the equilibrium field \mathbf{h}_0 can be written as $h_0\mathbf{m}_0$, where h_0 is now a scalar equal to $\mathbf{h}_0 \cdot \mathbf{m}_0$. To find oscillation modes, it is useful to split the magnetization \mathbf{m} and field \mathbf{h} into a static $(\mathbf{m}_0, \mathbf{h}_0)$ and a dynamic $(\delta\mathbf{m}, \delta\mathbf{h})$ part [6]:

$$\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{m}_0 + \delta\mathbf{m} \quad \mathbf{h} = \mathbf{h}_0 + \delta\mathbf{h} \quad (1.10)$$

$$\frac{\partial\mathbf{m}_0}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial\mathbf{h}_0}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

The search for spin waves now becomes the search for oscillation modes of $\delta\mathbf{m}$:

$$\frac{\partial\mathbf{m}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial\delta\mathbf{m}}{\partial t} = -(\mathbf{m}_0 + \delta\mathbf{m}) \times (h_0\mathbf{m}_0 + \delta\mathbf{h}) \quad (1.12)$$

$$= -(\mathbf{m}_0 \times \delta\mathbf{h} + \delta\mathbf{m} \times (h_0\mathbf{m}_0) + \underbrace{\delta\mathbf{m} \times \delta\mathbf{h}}_{\mathcal{O}(\delta\mathbf{m}^2)}) \quad (1.13)$$

$$= -\mathbf{m}_0 \times \delta\mathbf{h} + h_0\mathbf{m}_0 \times \delta\mathbf{m} \quad (1.14)$$

$$= \mathbf{m}_0 \times (-\delta\mathbf{h} + h_0\delta\mathbf{m}) \quad (1.15)$$

We now assume a linear dependence of $\delta\mathbf{h}$ from $\delta\mathbf{m}$, so

$$\delta\mathbf{h} = -\hat{\mathbf{N}}\delta\mathbf{m} \quad (1.16)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{N}}$ is an operator describing the magnetic interactions which does not depend on time. The linearized Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation can now be written as

$$\frac{\partial\delta\mathbf{m}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{m}_0 \times [(\hat{\mathbf{N}} + h_0\hat{\mathbf{I}})\delta\mathbf{m}] \quad (1.17)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ is the identity operator.

We can expand $\delta\mathbf{m}$ into individual oscillations to find a static LLG:

$$\delta\mathbf{m} = \sum_{\nu} e^{-i\omega_{\nu}t} \delta\mathbf{m}_{\nu} + \text{complex conjugate} \quad (1.18)$$

where $\delta\mathbf{m}_{\nu}$ does not depend on time, and the complex conjugate is added to obtain only real solutions. $\delta\mathbf{m}_{\nu}$ is also called the ‘‘mode profile’’. The evolution of a given mode in time can be obtained via

$$\delta\mathbf{m}(t) = e^{-i\omega t} \delta\mathbf{m} + e^{i\omega t} \delta\mathbf{m}^* = 2 \cos(\omega t) \text{Re}(\delta\mathbf{m}) + 2 \sin(\omega t) \text{Im}(\delta\mathbf{m}) \quad (1.19)$$

Because the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation is linear, each summand $e^{-i\omega_{\nu}t} \delta\mathbf{m}_{\nu}$ (and complex conjugate) solves it. Inserting this into the linearized LLG leads to (see also [6, eq. 52])

$$\omega_{\nu} \delta\mathbf{m}_{\nu} = i [\mathbf{m}_0 \times (\hat{\mathbf{N}} + h_0\hat{\mathbf{I}})] \delta\mathbf{m}_{\nu} \quad (1.20)$$

which is called the linearized Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation. This equation now is in the form of an eigenvalue problem, with ω_{ν} being the eigenvalue and

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}} := i [\mathbf{m}_0 \times (\hat{\mathbf{N}} + h_0\hat{\mathbf{I}})] \quad (1.21)$$

the operator, also called dynamic matrix. This dynamic matrix is hermitian. For every eigenvalue ω_{ν} and corresponding eigenvector $\delta\mathbf{m}_{\nu}$, $-\omega_{\nu}$ is also an eigenvalue and

the complex conjugate of $\delta\mathbf{m}$ the corresponding eigenvector.

Chapter 2

Implementation of a program calculating oscillation modes using an eigensolver

This chapter describes the implementation of a program capable of calculating spin waves using an eigensolver, implemented by the author.

There are three main ways to calculate spin-wave modes:

1. Analytical: In simple systems (for example, an infinitely extended film), oscillation modes can be approximated analytically [18]. This approach quickly becomes infeasible for complex systems.
2. Dynamic simulation: In this approach, the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation is solved via time integration. Using the Finite Element Method (FEM), a dynamic simulation can compute oscillation modes in arbitrary geometries. A dynamic simulation using the Finite Element Method is implemented in TetraMag [2], which is described in further detail in section 2.1.3. A special case of FEM is the Finite Differences Method (FDM), which is implemented in Mumax³ [1]. TetraMag and Mumax³ are used to calculate reference values for the dynamic matrix approach.
3. Dynamic matrix approach: This approach uses an eigensolver to directly find mode profiles and frequencies as solutions of the linearized LLG equation. This approach makes it possible to find energetically degenerate modes, and does not require the design of special excitation fields. Although it can only solve the damping-less and linearized LLG, damping rates and weakly nonlinear can later on be calculated from the obtained mode profiles and frequencies [7, 19][20, ch. 7].

To understand the implementation of the dynamic matrix approach presented in this thesis, it is necessary to understand the codebase and concepts it builds upon. This is described in the following section, where the concept of space discretization is outlined, and the equilibrium calculation and TetraMag are introduced. In section 2.2, the implementation of the dynamic matrix approach is presented. Alongside the implementation, the author will examine different test cases to verify that their implementation is correct.

2.1 Preexisting code

2.1.1 Space discretization in the Finite Element Method

In the Finite Element Method, the magnetization \mathbf{m} is not represented as a continuous field, but it is evaluated only at certain positions (“nodes”) $\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N$, where N is the number of nodes. These positions are given by a mesh of the considered object, which can be constructed with programs such as gmsh [21]. This allows all field and scalar variables to be represented as vectors which can be stored as numbers on a computer. For example, the entire magnetization for a given object is now represented as

$$\mathbf{m} \leftarrow \begin{pmatrix} m_x(\mathbf{r}_1) \\ m_x(\mathbf{r}_2) \\ \vdots \\ m_x(\mathbf{r}_N) \\ m_y(\mathbf{r}_1) \\ m_y(\mathbf{r}_2) \\ \vdots \\ m_y(\mathbf{r}_N) \\ m_z(\mathbf{r}_1) \\ m_z(\mathbf{r}_3) \\ \vdots \\ m_z(\mathbf{r}_N) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

where $m_i(\mathbf{r})$ is the i th component of the vector $\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r})$.

Operators (which may include derivatives with respect to space) can be represented as matrices. The matrix representations of ∇, ∇^2 are calculated using the Galerkin method [13], which is implemented in the Preproc executable (as part of TetraMag). Operators acting locally (not containing any derivatives or integrations with respect to space, but may be depending on the location \mathbf{r}) are made out of diagonal matrix blocks. Take an operator $\hat{\mathbf{N}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}))$, which we are going to discretize into the matrix \mathbf{N} :

$$\hat{\mathbf{N}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r})) =: \begin{pmatrix} N_{xx}(\mathbf{r}) & N_{xy}(\mathbf{r}) & N_{xz}(\mathbf{r}) \\ N_{yx}(\mathbf{r}) & N_{yy}(\mathbf{r}) & N_{yz}(\mathbf{r}) \\ N_{zx}(\mathbf{r}) & N_{zy}(\mathbf{r}) & N_{zz}(\mathbf{r}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} m_x(\mathbf{r}) \\ m_y(\mathbf{r}) \\ m_z(\mathbf{r}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.2)$$

$$\mathbf{N} := \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{N}_{xx} & \mathbf{N}_{xy} & \mathbf{N}_{xz} \\ \mathbf{N}_{yx} & \mathbf{N}_{yy} & \mathbf{N}_{yz} \\ \mathbf{N}_{zx} & \mathbf{N}_{zy} & \mathbf{N}_{zz} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.3)$$

$$N_{ij} = \text{diag}(N_{ij}(\mathbf{r}_1), N_{ij}(\mathbf{r}_2), \dots, N_{ij}(\mathbf{r}_N)) \quad (2.4)$$

Because the number of nodes N is usually large ($\sim 10^4$), matrices of dimension $N \times N$ or larger are saved in a sparse matrix format, which only stores nonzero elements and their positions.

2.1.2 Equilibrium calculation

For both the dynamical simulation approach and the dynamic matrix approach, the equilibrium magnetization \mathbf{m}_0 needs to be calculated.

There are two main methods to calculate the equilibrium magnetization of a material: Dynamical calculation and energy minimization. To calculate the equilibrium magnetization \mathbf{m}_0 dynamically, the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation (1.9) is solved by time integration. A high Gilbert damping parameter $\alpha \approx \frac{1}{2}$ is assumed so that the simulation converges faster to its equilibrium state. The equilibrium is found if the magnetization and magnetic field are parallel, so $|\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{H}| \approx 0$.

The other approach is to find the magnetization which minimizes the energy $E = \int \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{H} dV$. This method can be more efficient than the dynamical calculation. The TetraMagStat executable implements this energy minimization.

2.1.3 TetraMag

TetraMag is a program which allows for the dynamic simulation of spin systems using the Finite Element Method, implemented by A. Kákay [2][22] based on an original Fortran 77 version written by R. Hertel [23] (programs such as TetraMagStat and Preproc are part of the TetraMag suite). It provides functions to calculate the magnetic fields of interactions, with the option for GPU acceleration, which makes these functions run extremely efficiently.

In TetraMag, the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation is solved using time integration. This allows for the capturing of the magnetization as a function of time and space, $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}_i, t)$. The dynamical simulation of $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}_i, t)$ can also be used to investigate effects other than spin waves, such as domain wall motion, Skyrmion gyration and magnetization reversal.

To investigate oscillation modes using this method, the modes must be excited using an external field. Because the frequencies of the oscillation modes of a given object are of interest and not known beforehand, several frequencies must be excited at once. This is achieved using a field pulse with an amplitude that has a sinc-like dependence on time, because the sinc function excites all frequencies up to a given cutoff frequency equally (the FFT of a sinc function is a rectangular function). The spatial dependence of the field pulse amplitude needs to be carefully designed depending on the geometry of the given object, because otherwise not all oscillation modes might be discovered, as the energy transfer to the mode, $\int \delta \mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{H} dV$, can easily vanish. For example, a homogenous field pulse in a disk will never find an oscillation mode with an azimuthal node, because the energy transfer to that mode is zero. More modes will be found with a field pulse of the form $A(\rho, \phi) \propto \frac{\sin \rho}{\rho} [\sin \phi + \cos \phi]$ (where ρ, ϕ are cylindrical coordinates). This particular field pulse will not excite modes with more than one azimuthal nodes, and even if a field pulse could excite all modes at once, energetically degenerate modes cannot be dissected into individual mode profiles without knowledge of the structure of the individual modes. Of course, one of the reasons for FEM simulations is to *find* these mode structures. The need for a careful consideration of the field pulse amplitude is a clear disadvantage of the approach to calculate spin waves using a dynamical simulation.

To find the mode frequencies ω , a fast-Fourier-transform (FFT) is used on the magnetization of each individual node. The average of all spectra (over all nodes) shows the oscillation mode frequencies as peaks. Although the data produced by the FFTs is large (~ 100 GB), it would be unfeasible to just run a FFT on the average of all magnetizations: Whenever the average magnetization of a mode would be zero, it could not be detected by this FFT on the averages. However, many oscillation modes of interest possess exactly this property of having an average of zero.

Identifying the peaks in the FFT spectrum requires either human intervention or the calibration of a peak finder, either of which is a potentially error-prone process

(peaks might be identified at the wrong position, or not identified at all). The oscillation mode profile $\delta\mathbf{m}$ for a given frequency ω is equal to the amplitude and phase of the magnetization of each node at that frequency (which was found by the previous FFT).

2.2 Eigensolver implementation

A more direct approach to obtaining oscillation modes is using an eigensolver which solves the eigenvalue problem described in equation 2.8. This was implemented by the author in a combination of Python (operator construction and calling of eigensolver), C (construction of rotation matrices), and Cython (calling library functions of TetraMag). The implementation by the author is called “TetraEigen”. The eigensolver used is the “eigsh” solver provided by the ARPACK package [24] wrapped in SciPy [25]. To calculate the equilibrium magnetization, field, and ∇ , ∇^2 matrices, the existing TetraMag code provided by A. Kákay et al. [2][22] is used.

2.2.1 Rotated Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation

By rotating the magnetization into a different frame of reference, the size of the operator in the linearized LLG (eq. 1.20) can be reduced. This can speed up the calculation of eigenvectors using numerical eigensolvers, and is also described in [6] and [4, p. 2]. The rotation uses the fact that the magnitude of the magnetization \mathbf{m} is always equal to 1, meaning that $|\mathbf{m}_0 + \delta\mathbf{m}| = 1$ and therefore $\mathbf{m}_0 \cdot \delta\mathbf{m} = 0$.

We can now define a local reference frame of unit vectors $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3$ such that the dynamic magnetization component in \mathbf{e}_3 -direction is zero and can be omitted.

$$\mathbf{e}_3 := \mathbf{m}_0 \quad \mathbf{e}_2 := \frac{\mathbf{e}_z \times \mathbf{m}_0}{|\mathbf{e}_z \times \mathbf{m}_0|} \quad \mathbf{e}_1 := -\frac{\mathbf{m}_0 \times \mathbf{e}_2}{|\mathbf{m}_0 \times \mathbf{e}_2|} \quad (2.5)$$

This construction fails if the equilibrium magnetization \mathbf{m}_0 is exactly equal to \mathbf{e}_z . In this case, \mathbf{e}_1 is set to \mathbf{e}_x , \mathbf{e}_2 to \mathbf{e}_y and \mathbf{e}_3 to \mathbf{e}_z . Rotating \mathbf{m}_0 into the local reference frame will always result in the vector $(0, 0, 1)^T$. Rotating $\delta\mathbf{m}$ will result in the vector $(\delta\mathbf{m}_1, \delta\mathbf{m}_2, 0)^T$. Using the compact rotated dynamical magnetization

$$\delta\tilde{\mathbf{m}} := \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_x & \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_y & \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_z \\ \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_x & \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_y & \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_z \end{pmatrix}}_{=:R} \delta\mathbf{m} \quad (2.6)$$

the linearized LLG can be further compacted by multiplying with R from the left:

$$\omega_\nu R \delta\mathbf{m}_\nu = iR [\mathbf{m}_0 \times (\hat{\mathbf{N}} + h_0 \hat{\mathbf{I}})] \underbrace{R^T R \delta\mathbf{m}_\nu}_{=: \delta\mathbf{m}_\nu} \quad (2.7)$$

$$\omega_\nu \delta\tilde{\mathbf{m}}_\nu = iR [\mathbf{m}_0 \times (\hat{\mathbf{N}} + h_0 \hat{\mathbf{I}})] R^T \delta\tilde{\mathbf{m}}_\nu \quad (2.8)$$

which is again an eigenvalue problem, with the dynamic matrix

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}} := iR [\mathbf{m}_0 \times (\hat{\mathbf{N}} + h_0 \hat{\mathbf{I}})] R^T \quad (2.9)$$

This dynamic matrix is of dimension $2N \times 2N$, while the dimension of the dynamic matrix before the rotation was $3N \times 3N$. This is the matrix provided to the eigensolver in TetraEigen.

In the FEM discretization, \mathbf{R} is represented as a matrix of six blocks:

$$\mathbf{R} \leftarrow \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{1x} & \mathbf{R}_{1y} & \mathbf{R}_{1z} \\ \mathbf{R}_{2x} & \mathbf{R}_{2y} & \mathbf{R}_{2z} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.10)$$

where each block is of dimension $N \times N$, and each block can be described as

$$\mathbf{R}_{1x} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{e}_1(\mathbf{r}_1) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_1(\mathbf{r}_2) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x, \dots, \mathbf{e}_1(\mathbf{r}_N) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x) \quad (2.11)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{1y} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{e}_1(\mathbf{r}_1) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_1(\mathbf{r}_2) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y, \dots, \mathbf{e}_1(\mathbf{r}_N) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y) \quad (2.12)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{2x} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{e}_2(\mathbf{r}_1) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_2(\mathbf{r}_2) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x, \dots, \mathbf{e}_2(\mathbf{r}_N) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x) \quad (2.13)$$

$$\vdots \quad (2.14)$$

The cross product with \mathbf{m}_0 in equation 1.20 can also be represented by a matrix $\mathbf{m}_{0 \times}$. There is no need to calculate this matrix explicitly, as it is much easier to calculate its rotated version

$$\tilde{\mathbf{m}}_{0 \times} := \mathbf{R} \mathbf{m}_{0 \times} \mathbf{R}^T = \begin{pmatrix} 0_N & -\mathbb{1}_N \\ \mathbb{1}_N & 0_N \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.15)$$

2.2.2 Structure of mode calculation

The structure of mode calculation using TetraEigen is as follows:

1. The program Preproc is executed to calculate the Galerkin ∇ , ∇^2 matrices and matrices for the dipolar interaction.
2. TetraMagStat is executed to calculate the equilibrium magnetization \mathbf{m}_0 using an energy minimization algorithm.
3. TetraEigen (implemented by the author) is executed, which follows these steps:
 - (a) The rotation matrix is constructed (implemented in C).
 - (b) The equilibrium field \mathbf{h}_0 is calculated using the equilibrium magnetization \mathbf{m}_0 given by TetraMagStat and functions from TetraMag (implemented in C).
 - (c) The interaction operators $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_i$ are constructed (implemented in C, Python and Cython; sec. 2.2.4). This requires a reimplemention of the interaction as a matrix instead of a function in the case of the anisotropic and IDMI interactions, and a translation from C to Cython/Python in the case of the dipolar interaction.
 - (d) The interaction operators $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_i$ are added together to provide the overall field operator $\hat{\mathbf{N}}$, and combined with the cross product operator $\mathbf{m}_{0 \times}$ and the rotation matrices \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{R}^T to provide the dynamic matrix,

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}} = i\mathbf{R} [\mathbf{m}_0 \times (\hat{\mathbf{N}} + h_0 \hat{\mathbf{I}})] \mathbf{R}^T \quad (2.16)$$

This step is implemented in Python using SciPy [25] sparse matrix library functions.

- (e) An object representing the inverse of the dynamic matrix is computed (sec. 2.2.3) in order to increase the speed of the eigensolver. If the dipolar interaction is not considered, this is simply the inverse of the dynamic matrix. If the dipolar interaction is considered, the inverse is computed for

a given vector using the LGMRES algorithm [26][27] with an appropriate preconditioner.

- (f) The eigensolver is called using the dynamic matrix and inverse object, returning the desired number of spin wave frequencies and oscillation mode profiles (sec. 2.2.3).
- (g) The oscillation mode profiles are rotated from the local reference frame to the global reference frame using the already calculated rotation matrix. The frequencies are converted from dimensionless to SI units.

2.2.3 Eigensolver call

To solve the eigenvalue problem, the dynamic matrix $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ defined in equation 2.9 is passed to the SciPy `sparse.linalg.eigsh` function, which is a wrapper around ARPACK [24] functions using the Implicitly Restarted Lanczos Method. The Lanczos algorithm is essentially a power method, meaning that it arrives at the eigenvectors and eigenvalues for a given problem by reapplying the matrix in question several times.

Eigensolver tolerance

The eigensolver `eigsh` stops once a certain relative accuracy of the eigenvalues is reached, which is called the “eigensolver tolerance” here. This value is supplied as the parameter `tol` to the `eigsh` function. One thing to keep in mind is that, due to errors introduced by the FEM discretization, the eigensolver tolerance is not the same as the real relative accuracy of the eigenvalues.

FIGURE 2.1: Dependency of the gyromode frequency f_0 in a disk with radius 100 nm and width 30 nm from the eigensolver tolerance. Lower tolerances require significantly more computation time when the dipolar interaction is considered.

Operator inversion

By nature, the Lanczos algorithm is more efficient at finding large eigenvalues. In the search for spin waves, however, only the lowest frequencies (and, in consequence,

energies) are of interest (the exchange interaction, for example, is only correctly calculated using equation 1.2 in the limit of low energies). To overcome this challenge, the eigensolver is used in “shift-invert” mode, which enables the eigensolver to find eigenvalues near a given value σ , in this case $\sigma = 0$ (as in this thesis, only the lowest eigenvalues are desired – if desired, however, spin-waves at arbitrary frequencies can be found by changing σ). The shift-invert algorithm has to solve the equation $(\hat{\mathbf{G}} - \sigma\mathbb{1})\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$ for \mathbf{x} , which becomes $\hat{\mathbf{G}}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$ in the case $\sigma = 0$. In other words, it needs to know the inverse of $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$, which can be supplied as the parameter `OPinv` to the `eigsh` function.

If $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ is a sparse matrix, the parameter `OPinv` is not supplied, and SciPy automatically calculates the inverse of $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ as a sparse LU decomposition.

If the dipolar interaction is considered, $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ is not a sparse matrix, and so a sparse matrix inversion is not possible. In this case, `OPinv` is supplied as a `LinearOperator` object, which allows for an on-demand calculation of $\hat{\mathbf{G}}^{-1}\mathbf{b}$. The inverse calculation is implemented using the SciPy `sparse.linalg.lgmres` function, which solves the problem $\hat{\mathbf{G}}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$ for \mathbf{x} without knowing the matrix elements of $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ by implementing the LGMRES algorithm [26, 27]. The LGMRES algorithm can be optimized by supplying a preconditioner, which is an approximation of the inverse of the $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ operator, as a parameter. This preconditioner is implemented as an incomplete LU decomposition of the sparse part of the $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ operator,

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{\text{sparse}} := i\mathbf{R} [\mathbf{m}_0 \times (\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ex} + \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{an} + \hat{\mathbf{N}}_{dmi} + h_0\hat{\mathbf{I}})] \mathbf{R}^T \quad (2.17)$$

The LGMRES algorithm also accepts an argument `tol`, which is the relative accuracy of the inverted vectors. By default, this argument is set to the same value as the eigensolver tolerance, but `TetraEigen` allows to set it to a different value manually.

2.2.4 Implementation of interactions

Exchange interaction and external field

The exchange field can be calculated using the exchange operator $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ex} = -\Lambda_{ex}^2 \nabla^2$ (see equation 1.2). Using the Galerkin method, this operator can simply be represented as a matrix. This matrix is already provided by the `Preproc` program.

To verify that the implementation of this interaction is correct, let us examine a flat cuboid with an external out-of-plane field applied, such that it is homogeneously magnetized. If only the exchange interaction is considered (next to the external field), the lowest oscillation frequency should be equal to the Larmor frequency, $\omega_L = \gamma\mu_0|\mathbf{H}_{ext}|$ (ω_L in SI units, not dimensionless), where $|\mathbf{H}_{ext}|$ is the magnitude of the applied external field and $\gamma > 0$ is the absolute value of the gyromagnetic ratio. At this frequency, the magnetization vectors precess in phase and with the same amplitude.

Running `TetraEigen` on an example case with an external field in z -direction $\mu_0|\mathbf{H}_{ext}| = 10$ mT and an eigensolver tolerance of 10^{-8} on a rectangle with dimensions $300 \text{ nm} \times 100 \text{ nm} \times 20 \text{ nm}$, the result of the `TetraEigen` program is:

$$\text{TetraEigen:} \quad f_L = \frac{\omega_L}{2\pi} = 0.280\,249\,52 \text{ GHz} \quad (2.18)$$

$$\text{Theory:} \quad f_L = \gamma \cdot 10 \text{ mT} = 0.280\,249\,52 \text{ GHz} \quad (2.19)$$

The coincidence of these values is an indicator for the proper implementation of the exchange interaction.

Oscillation modes at higher energies in this system are harmonic waves with frequency

$$\omega = \gamma\mu_0(|\mathbf{k}|^2\Lambda_{ex}^2 M_s + |\mathbf{H}_{ext}|) \quad (2.20)$$

where \mathbf{k} is the wave vector. This can easily be proven by examining the eigenvectors of the operator (from the linearized LLG, see equation 1.20)

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}} := i \underbrace{\mathbf{m}_0}_{\mathbf{e}_z} \times (-\Lambda_{ex}^2 \nabla^2 + |\mathbf{h}_{ext}| \mathbb{1}) \quad (2.21)$$

which are of the form

$$\delta\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{A} \exp(i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}) \quad (2.22)$$

There is only one possible amplitude \mathbf{A} which fulfills

$$\mathbf{A} = i\mathbf{e}_z \times \mathbf{A} \quad \implies \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} a \\ ia \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad a \in \mathbb{C} \quad (2.23)$$

Possible wave vectors are selected by the boundary condition

$$\text{Re } \hat{\mathbf{G}}\delta\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}_b) = i\mathbf{A}(|\mathbf{k}|^2\Lambda_{ex}^2 + |\mathbf{h}_{ext}|) \sin(\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}) \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \quad (2.24)$$

$$\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r} \stackrel{!}{=} \pi n \quad n \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (2.25)$$

where \mathbf{r}_b is on the surface of the cuboid. This boundary condition is a consequence of the fact that the dynamic magnetization $\delta\mathbf{m}$ must be zero outside of the ferromagnetic material.

These oscillation modes were found by TetraEigen, and their corresponding frequencies are compared with the theoretical prediction in table 2.1. Although these frequencies were calculated with an eigensolver tolerance of 10^{-8} , the frequencies returned by TetraEigen do not share 8 significant digits with the theoretical prediction. This is most probably caused by the discretization.

$k_x (\frac{2\pi}{L_x})$	$k_y (\frac{2\pi}{L_y})$	TetraEigen f (GHz)	Theory f (GHz)
0	0	0.280 249 52	0.280 249 51
1/2	0	0.380 638 47	0.380 661 44
2/2	0	0.681 529 69	0.681 897 24
1/2	1/2	1.282 451 1	1.284 368 8
3/2	0	1.182 584 7	1.183 956 9
2/2	1/2	1.583 335 7	1.585 604 6
4/2	0	1.880 964 0	1.886 840 4
3/2	1/2	2.083 887 7	2.087 664 3
5/2	0	2.775 682 1	2.790 547 8

TABLE 2.1: Comparison of theoretically predicted and calculated eigenmodes in a cuboid element with length $L_x = 300$ nm, width $L_y = 100$ nm and exchange length $\Lambda_{ex} = 5.716$ nm when only the exchange interaction and an external field is considered.

FIGURE 2.2: Frequencies of spin-waves in a cuboid element, calculated by TetraEigen and using the theoretical prediction. This plot uses data from table 2.1, and clearly shows the parabolic dispersion relation expected from the exchange interaction.

Anisotropy interaction

The existing TetraMag code already implements several types of anisotropy: uniaxial, cubic, and surface anisotropy (which, in practice, can be used to represent any anisotropy with a dependence of the anisotropy axis \mathbf{u} from the location \mathbf{r} , including a shape anisotropy). Uniaxial and surface anisotropy are also implemented in TetraEigen. Because anisotropies are purely local, their matrix representation is a matrix consisting of diagonal blocks. For a given location \mathbf{r} , the anisotropy operator $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{ani}$ is given as (see section 1.2.3)

$$\hat{\mathbf{N}}_{an} = -\frac{2K_{u1}(\mathbf{r})}{\mu_0 M_s^2} \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}) \otimes \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2.26)$$

To test the implementation of the uniaxial anisotropy in TetraEigen, let us again consider a flat cuboid element without an external field applied, but with a uniaxial in-plane anisotropy. The equilibrium field then is parallel to the anisotropy vector, which we set to \mathbf{e}_x in this example. The oscillation modes of this system should solve the linearized LLG

$$\omega \delta \mathbf{m} = i \mathbf{m}_0 \times \left[(-\Lambda_{ex}^2 \nabla^2) \delta \mathbf{m} - \frac{2K_{u1}}{\mu_0 M_s^2} (\delta \mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{e}_x) \mathbf{e}_x + h_0 \delta \mathbf{m} \right] \quad (2.27)$$

$$h_0 = \mathbf{m}_0 \cdot \mathbf{h}_0 = \frac{2K_{u1}}{\mu_0 M_s^2} \quad (2.28)$$

The solutions then are of the form

$$\delta \mathbf{m} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ a \\ ia \end{pmatrix}}_A \exp(i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}) \quad a \in \mathbb{C} \quad (2.29)$$

$$\omega = \gamma\mu_0 M_s \left(\frac{2K_{u1}}{\mu_0 M_s^2} + |\mathbf{k}|^2 \Lambda_{ex}^2 \right) \quad (2.30)$$

Again, these modes were found by TetraEigen with an eigensolver tolerance of 10^{-8} . Their frequencies can be found in table 2.2. Like with the exchange interaction, the lowest frequency is the most accurate, and the following frequencies are disturbed by the discretization.

$k_x (\frac{2\pi}{L_x})$	$k_y (\frac{2\pi}{L_y})$	TetraEigen f (GHz)	Theory f (GHz)
0	0	0.704 343 86	0.704 343 86
1/2	0	0.804 732 82	0.804 755 79
2/2	0	1.105 624 0	1.105 991 6
1/2	1/2	1.706 545 5	1.708 463 2
2/2	1/2	2.007 430 0	2.009 699 0
4/2	0	2.305 058 4	2.310 934 8
3/2	1/2	2.507 982 0	2.511 758 6
5/2	0	3.199 776 4	3.214 642 1
5/2	1/2	4.101 861 8	4.118 349 5
1/2	2/2	4.389 317 4	4.419 585 3

TABLE 2.2: Comparison of theoretically predicted and calculated eigenmodes in a cuboid element with length $L_x = 300$ nm, width $L_y = 100$ nm and exchange length $\Lambda_{ex} = 5.716$ nm, when exchange interaction and anisotropy are considered.

Interfacial Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction (IDMI)

This interaction, similar to the exchange interaction, is short-ranged and can be described by combining the ∇ matrix and the surface normal vector \mathbf{n} (see equation 1.6), both provided by the Preproc program. The IDMI is necessary to explain the stability of magnetic skyrmions, so a good test for a correct implementation is to compare mode frequencies and profiles of magnetic skyrmions with previous numerical calculations. A micromagnetic simulation was performed by Kornienko et al. [28], who studied spin waves of skyrmions in Gaussian bumps of different curvature (amplitude). The author used TetraEigen on the same problem, but the resulting eigenfrequencies were imaginary, indicating a non-hermitian operator, which indicates a wrong implementation. The cause of this error is yet to be found. Curiously, the IDMI field calculated by the operator (which was implemented by the author) when applied to the equilibrium magnetization is parallel to the IDMI function implemented in TetraMag: With a maximum angular deviation of 3.0×10^{-8} rad and a maximum vector modulus deviation of

$$\max \left(\frac{|\mathbf{H}_{\text{operator}}|}{|\mathbf{H}_{\text{TetraMag}}|} - 1 \right) = 0.45 \quad (2.31)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{\text{operator}}$ is the field calculated by the operator implemented by the author, and $\mathbf{H}_{\text{TetraMag}}$ is the field calculated by the corresponding TetraMag function.

Dipolar interaction

The dipolar interaction is the hardest interaction to implement, as it is not local and not even short-ranged. This means that although it *could* be represented as a matrix, this matrix would be dense, meaning it would have few nonzero entries, thereby requiring working memory in the order of 10 GB (for $N \sim 10^5$). Instead, the demagnetizing field is calculated on-demand with functions provided by TetraMag, by implementing the dipolar interaction operator as a SciPy `sparse.linalg.LinearOperator` class. Because the dynamical magnetization $\delta\mathbf{m}$ can be complex, but the functions of TetraMag only deal with real numbers, the imaginary and real component of the demagnetizing field are calculated in parallel. A single field calculation of the demagnetizing field (“matrix multiplication”) requires two systems of equations with $3N$ variables to be solved, which means this operation takes a long time to complete compared to a simple sparse matrix-vector multiplication.

The gyrotropic motion mode of a magnetic vortex (which, itself, can only be stable with the dipolar interaction) in a thin disk only appears if the dipolar interaction is considered, which makes the gyromode frequency a good test for a correct implementation. This gyromode frequency has been studied semi-analytically [29] in the limit of $\frac{L}{R} \ll 1$, and is equal to

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{9\pi} \frac{\gamma\mu_0 M_s}{4\pi\chi_0} \quad \text{with} \quad \frac{1}{\chi_0} = 9.98 \frac{L}{R} \quad (2.32)$$

where L is the height and R the radius of the disk in question.

This oscillation mode has been simulated in both TetraEigen (by the author) und Mumax³ [1] (by L. Körber) in a disk with $L = 30$ nm and $R = 100$ nm. The resulting mode profile (calculated in TetraEigen) can be seen in figure 2.3. The frequency of the gyromode was calculated to be:

$$\text{Theory:} \quad f_0 = \frac{1}{9\pi} \frac{9.98\gamma\mu_0 M_s L}{4\pi R} = 1.484 \text{ GHz} \quad (2.33)$$

$$\text{TetraEigen:} \quad f_0 = 1.038 \text{ GHz} \quad (2.34)$$

$$\text{Mumax}^3: \quad f_0 = 1.04 \text{ GHz} \quad (2.35)$$

where an eigensolver tolerance of 10^{-4} was used. The result of TetraEigen matches up with the frequency calculated by Mumax³, but both deviate from the theoretical prediction. This could be because $\frac{L}{R} = 0.3 \ll 1$. Simulating disks with larger radius while still resolving the vortex core requires more memory to compute the dipolar interaction, because the mesh contains more nodes. This is the reason why in this thesis, mostly very small objects ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) are simulated. For the radii $R = 100$ nm, 150 nm, . . . , 500 nm, the gyrofrequencies were calculated using an eigensolver tolerance of 10^{-3} . The results are presented in figure 2.4. Both Mumax³ and TetraEigen show the gyromode frequency $f \propto R^{-1}$ proportionality predicted by the theory. They seem to be offset, however, by a factor from the theoretical prediction. This could be due to discretization errors which distort the vortex core, or due to $\frac{L}{R} \ll 1$.

FIGURE 2.3: Equilibrium magnetization and gyrotropic oscillation mode in a thin disk with radius 100 nm and thickness 30 nm, plotted is the dimensionless magnetization. In pictures 2.3a and 2.3b, one can see the typical vortex structure which arises as a result of the dipolar interaction. In pictures 2.3c and 2.3d, the gyrotropic motion of the vortex core can be recognized, as the vortex is “shifted” towards areas where the z component of the magnetization is positive and away from areas where the z component of the magnetization is negative.

FIGURE 2.4: Comparison of gyromode frequencies calculated using TetraEigen, Mumax³ and the formula provided by Gusliencko [29] for a disk with varying radius and height $h = 30$ nm. Mumax³ and TetraEigen calculate frequencies below the predicted theory value, but their frequencies follow the predicted $f \propto R^{-1}$ proportionality. An apparent exception is the gyromode frequency at $R = 200$ nm, where TetraEigen calculates a value which is greater than the frequency for $R = 150$ nm. The difference between the frequencies calculated by Mumax³ and TetraEigen cannot only be explained by the eigensolver tolerance of TetraEigen, as their relative difference is in the order of 10^{-2} to 10^{-1} , while the eigensolver tolerance is 10^{-3} .

Chapter 3

Applications

In the following sections, TetraEigen is applied to two variations of a disk to observe the change in spin-wave frequencies and profiles: In the first section, the disk is curved into the shape of a hemisphere, and in the next section, an external in-plane field is applied to shift the vortex core.

In a disk, spin-wave modes are usually classified using the azimuthal mode index m and the radial mode index n . The radial mode index n is defined here as the number of zero-crossings of the out-of-plane component of the magnetization in radial direction (from the vortex core to the edge of the disk). The azimuthal mode index m can be defined as the integer for which

$$\delta \mathbf{m} \propto e^{im\phi} \Psi(\rho) \quad (3.1)$$

where ϕ, ρ are the cylindrical coordinates, and $\Psi(\rho)$ is the radial profile of the mode (see [20, ch. 4.1]).

3.1 Hemisphere

exchange constant A_{ex}	13 pJ m^{-1}
saturation magnetization $\mu_0 M_s$	1 T
cell size	4 nm
thickness L	25 nm
radius R	80 nm
number of calculated modes	60

TABLE 3.1: Simulation parameters used for the hemisphere.

It has already been found analytically that the vortex core reversal in a hemisphere should depend on the polarization of the vortex core [30], and as a result of the curvature the in-plane circulation of the magnetization is not anymore concentric but shows an inward or outward spiral [31]. To further study the spin-waves in a hemisphere, let us examine them using TetraEigen. Modes were calculated on a hemisphere with radius $R = 80 \text{ nm}$ and thickness $L = 25 \text{ nm}$ (for additional simulation parameters, see table 3.1). The equilibrium magnetization in a hemisphere will form a vortex, like in the case of a disk. Because the curvature of the hemisphere breaks its symmetry, it is not guaranteed that spin-wave modes will be equal in an “up-core” (center magnetization in positive z -direction) and a “down-core” (center magnetization in negative z -direction) vortex. Therefore, two simulations were run, one in an up-core and one in a down-core equilibrium (see figure 3.1). For comparison, spin-wave modes were also calculated on a disk with radius $R = 125 \text{ nm}$

and thickness $L = 25$ nm, such that the diameter of the disk roughly equals the perimeter of the hemisphere.

FIGURE 3.1: Equilibrium magnetizations in the up-core and down-core hemisphere with radius $R = 80$ nm and thickness $L = 25$ nm. The opening of the hemisphere points in negative z -direction.

The result of these simulations can be seen in figure 3.2. For $|m| = 0, 1$, the radial mode index n could not be determined with absolute certainty on the hemisphere. The z -component of these modes is therefore given in the appendix in sections A.2 and A.3 (for comparison, the profiles of the corresponding modes in the reference disk are also given).

In the hemisphere, mode U31/D31 (see figure 3.3) stands out as exceptionally asymmetric ($|m| = 1, n = 2$). This is probably made possible by the curvature of the hemisphere, which is missing in the reference disk. Although the mode profiles in the up-core and down-core hemisphere often look similar, in this case they differ on the outside of the hemisphere. Inside of the hemisphere, however, they look very similar.

It is apparent that the vortex core magnetization direction (up or down) has no visible impact on the spin-wave frequencies. However, the spin-wave frequencies differ significantly between the reference disk and the hemisphere. For $|m| > 3$,

FIGURE 3.2: Spin-wave frequencies in a flat (“reference”) disk and a hemisphere with up-core and down-core magnetization. Spin-wave modes are categorized according to their azimuthal mode index $|m|$ and their radial mode index n . Additionally, a mode ID is displayed next to the modes for which $|m| = 0, 1$, which allows them to be identified with the mode profiles in the appendix. In the “combined” picture, the markers from the reference disk and the up/down-core hemisphere are overlaid, which shows that the frequencies for spin-waves in the up-core and down-core hemisphere are equal.

FIGURE 3.3: Mode U31/D31 ($|m| = 1, n = 2$) on the up-core and down-core hemisphere. The z-component of the real part of the dynamical magnetization is shown.

the spin-wave frequencies in the hemisphere are always greater than the spin-wave frequencies in the reference disk. This could be because the outer nodes are closer together in the hemisphere than in the reference disk, leading to a higher exchange energy for these modes.

Another effect is the mode splitting which occurs for $|m| = 1, 2$. For $|m| = 1$, this has already been observed in experiments [32], and is explained by an interaction with the gyrotropic motion of the vortex core.

3.2 Shifted vortex-core

Applying an in-plane external field to a disk will shift its vortex-core transversal to the field, thereby breaking the cylindrical symmetry (see figure 3.4). Analytically separating the linearized LLG into an azimuthal and a radial component in this case has not yet been possible. Experimentally (either in the lab or in dynamic simulations) finding modes is hard, as the mode profiles are not known beforehand and therefore are difficult to excite [20, ch. 6.2]. However, using TetraEigen, calculating spin-wave profiles and frequencies is just as easy as doing so in a normal disk without external magnetic field. This can help to study three-magnon scattering in vortex-state disks [20].

exchange constant A_{ex}	13 pJ m^{-1}
saturation magnetization $\mu_0 M_s$	1 T
cell size	5 nm
thickness L	15 nm
radius R	200 nm
external field B_x	15 mT
number of calculated modes	60

TABLE 3.2: Simulation parameters used for the disk with shifted vortex.

Modes were calculated on a disk with radius $R = 200 \text{ nm}$, thickness $L = 15 \text{ nm}$ and external in-plane field $B_x = 15 \text{ mT}$ (see also table 3.2). The resulting frequencies can be seen in figure 3.5. For many modes, the azimuthal mode index m and radial mode index n could not be determined, because the modes were irregular and sometimes even asymmetric.

In general, the shifted vortex core leads to a distortion of the modes, as can be seen in figure 3.6. Presumably, the exchange interaction causes a weaker out-of-plane magnetization in the narrow tunnel between vortex core and disk edge.

Up until now, all modes with $|m| > 0$ were *rotating* around the vortex core, so the imaginary part of the magnetization was always a rotation of its real part, which can be seen very well in figure 3.6. On the shifted-vortex disk, however, this is not always the case, as can be seen in figure 3.7. This mode seems to behave like a standing spin-wave, with nodes on the edge of the disk where the dynamical magnetization is always zero.

In figure 3.8, a spin-wave profile can be observed in which several domains melt together. While the outer domains move counterclockwise along the disk, the inner domains move clockwise, separating from and reconnecting to different outer domains. This pattern of different domains connecting in the inner parts of the disk can also be observed in other modes, for example 3.9.

FIGURE 3.4: Equilibrium magnetization of the shifted-vortex disk. The external field points in positive x -direction. The z -component of the magnetization is shown using a colormap, while arrows indicate the in-plane magnetization.

FIGURE 3.5: Spin-wave frequencies in a reference disk (no external field applied) and a disk with shifted vortex (external field applied). Again, spin-wave profiles are categorized using the azimuthal mode index $|m|$ and the radial mode index n . The “combined” picture displays the markers of the reference disk and shifted-vortex disk overlaid, which shows that the spin-wave frequencies in both disks are largely the same for $|m| > 1$. Many mode profiles found are not included into this graph, as they could not be classified.

One example for a particularly asymmetric mode is given in figure 3.10. This asymmetry is made possible by the breaking of the cylindrical symmetry by the external magnetic field. However, an asymmetric mode was also found in the reference disk, see figure 3.11. It could be that the discretization can cause spontaneous breaking of symmetry, which would also mean that spin-wave modes in the shifted-vortex disk might be more symmetric in reality than calculated here.

The “butterfly” modes described by L. Körber [20] were not found by TetraEigen, because they are relatively high-energy (high $|m|$) and only 60 different modes were calculated by TetraEigen.

(A) shifted-vortex disk, real part

(B) shifted-vortex disk, imaginary part

(C) reference disk, real part

(D) reference disk, imaginary part

FIGURE 3.6: Spin-wave mode with $|m| = 3, n = 0$ in the shifted-vortex disk and the reference disk. The z -component of the magnetization is displayed. Both real and imaginary component of the magnetization are shown to give a feeling for how the spin waves rotate.

(A) shifted-vortex disk, real part

(B) shifted-vortex disk, imaginary part

(C) reference disk, real part

(D) reference disk, imaginary part

FIGURE 3.7: Spin-wave mode with $|m| = 6, n = 0$ in the shifted-vortex disk and the reference disk. The z -component of the magnetization is displayed. Note how the amplitude of the real part of the out-of-plane magnetization in the shifted-vortex disk is significantly weaker than the imaginary component, indicating that this mode behaves more like a standing wave and not like a rotating spin wave.

FIGURE 3.8: In the shifted-vortex disk, the domains of an oscillation can melt together. This mode was classified as $|m| = 8, n = 0$.

FIGURE 3.9: Another mode in the shifted-vortex disk which shows the domains of the oscillation melt together. This mode was not assigned an azimuthal or radial mode index.

(A) real part

(B) imaginary part

FIGURE 3.10: Spin-wave mode with (presumably) $|m| = 1, n = 1$ in the shifted-vortex disk.

(A) real part

(B) imaginary part

FIGURE 3.11: Spin-wave mode with $|m| = 1, n = 1$ in the reference disk. This mode is asymmetric, although this is not expected.

Chapter 4

Conclusion and outlook

In this thesis, TetraEigen, a spin-wave calculator using the dynamic matrix approach, was implemented by the author. This program can be applied to study linear dynamics in magnetic systems. In contrast to the usual field pulse induced dynamic simulations, this approach resolves energetically degenerate spin-wave modes. Because TetraEigen uses the Finite Element Method, it is even possible to calculate spin-wave modes in arbitrary confined geometries.

Tests were made with the intention to confirm the correct implementation of the exchange, interfacial Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya (IDMI) and dipolar interaction, as well as magnetic anisotropy and external field. The results obtained with TetraEigen are in good agreement with analytical calculations or micromagnetic simulations for the exchange interaction, dipolar interaction and anisotropy. However, the predicted spin-wave frequencies do not match previous calculations from Kornienko et al. [28] in a test case where the IDMI was considered. The tests also showed that the memory required to calculate the demagnetizing field puts a limit on the size of the simulated objects.

Two particular examples have been chosen as real spin-wave mode study cases. Firstly, the effect of curvature on the spin-wave modes in a hemisphere was studied. It was found that the equilibrium vortex core magnetization (up or down) has no impact on the spin-wave frequencies of the hemisphere. The modes calculated were similar to those found in a reference flat disk. In both the hemisphere and the reference disk, the splitting of frequencies which occurs due to their interaction with the gyrotropic motion of the vortex core for small azimuthal mode indices $|m|$ has been observed. The frequencies of modes with azimuthal mode index $|m| > 3$ were higher than the corresponding modes in the reference disk. This can be explained by the smaller radius of the hemisphere leading to a higher exchange energy for these modes. An asymmetric spin-wave mode was discovered.

Secondly, the effect of symmetry-breaking on the modes in a flat disk with vortex state was studied. To break the circular symmetry an external field was applied, leading to a shifted vortex core towards the edge of the disk. This is a typical example for which the usual field pulse driven dynamic simulations have difficulties obtaining the possible spin-wave modes. This example was chosen to support the theoretical and experimental studies of three-magnon scattering in vortex disks.

Although many spin-wave profiles clearly corresponded to the ones found in the reference disk without external field, even showing similar frequencies, some profiles could not be classified because of their irregular pattern. Some modes looked like modes one would find in the reference disk, but with some of their domains melted together. These modes and their frequencies will be input parameters for rate equations to study three-magnon scattering.

For simulating larger problems, it is necessary to decrease the memory consumption of TetraEigen. This can be done by compressing the matrices used for the

calculation of the demagnetizing field, which is already implemented by TetraMag but not used in TetraEigen. The calculation of the demagnetizing field can be further optimized by using GPUs, which is also already implemented in TetraMag.

The dynamic matrix approach implemented in TetraEigen can only be used in confined systems. To study the spin-wave transport in extended waveguides, propagating wave solutions need to be considered. By changing the operators of TetraEigen appropriately it is possible to simulate spin waves in infinitely extended waveguides with arbitrary cross sections.

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Appendix A

Supplementary figures

A.1 Flat Disk

This section displays spin-wave modes in the disk which was used as a reference for comparison with modes on a hemisphere, see section 3.1. The z -component of the real part of the dynamic magnetization $\delta\mathbf{m}$ is shown.

FIGURE A.1: reference disk, modes with azimuthal index $m = 0$ are displayed

FIGURE A.2: reference disk, modes with azimuthal index $|m| = 1$ are displayed

FIGURE A.3: reference disk, modes with azimuthal index $|m| = 1$ are displayed

A.2 Up-Core Hemisphere

This section shows spin-wave modes in the hemisphere with an up-core equilibrium magnetization, see section 3.1. The opening of the hemisphere points in negative z -direction. The z -component of the real part of the dynamic magnetization $\delta\mathbf{m}$ is shown.

FIGURE A.4: up-core hemisphere, modes with azimuthal index $m = 0$ are displayed

FIGURE A.5: up-core hemisphere, modes with azimuthal index $|m| = 1$ are displayed

(A) $n = 2$ (U33)

(B) $n = 2$ (U33), side view

(C) $n = 2$ (U38)

(D) $n = 2$ (U38), side view

(E) $n = 3$ (U46)

(F) $n = 4$ (U53)

FIGURE A.6: up-core hemisphere, modes with azimuthal index $|m| = 1$ are displayed

A.3 Down-Core Hemisphere

This section shows spin-wave modes in the hemisphere with an down-core equilibrium magnetization, see section 3.1. The opening of the hemisphere points in negative z -direction. The z -component of the real part of the dynamic magnetization $\delta\mathbf{m}$ is shown.

FIGURE A.7: down-core hemisphere, modes with azimuthal index $m = 0$ are displayed

FIGURE A.8: down-core hemisphere, modes with azimuthal index $|m| = 1$ are displayed

FIGURE A.9: down-core hemisphere, modes with azimuthal index $|m| = 1$ are displayed

Declaration of Authorship

Hiermit erkläre ich, Gwendolyn Quasebarth, dass ich diese Abschlussarbeit "Calculation of spin-wave eigenmodes in confined nanostructures using a dynamic matrix approach" im Rahmen der Betreuung am Insitut für Ionenstrahlphysik und Materialforschung des Helmholtz-Zentrums Dresden - Rossendorf ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter verfasst und alle Quellen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Gezeichnet:

Datum:
